

EU-DREAM

Effective Uptake of Digital Services to Repower European Consumers and Communities as Active Participants in Energy Transition and Markets

D2.3 AI-based assistant tool

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ACRONYMS

ACRONYMS	
AC	Alternating Current
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMS	Battery Management System
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DC	Direct Current
DR	Demand Response
DT	Digital Twin
DTO	Digital Twin Orchestrator
EMS	Energy Management System
EV	Electric Vehicle
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
LightGBM	Light Gradient Boosting Machine
LL	Living Lab
LP	Linear Programming
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MCB	Miniature Circuit Breaker
MILP	Mixed-Integer Linear Programming
MOLR	Multi-Output Linear Regression
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OPSD	Open Power System Data
POD	Point of Delivery
PV	Photovoltaic
RCBO	Residual Current Breaker with Overcurrent Protection
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RF	Random Forest
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SoC	State of Charge
ToU	Time-of-Use
TPE	Tree-structured Parzen Estimator
WP	Work Package

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the work carried out under Task 2.3 – AI-based Assistant Tool, covering activities from M4 to M18 and laying the foundation for an intelligent, user-centric energy optimisation service integrated into the EU-DREAM digital ecosystem.

The task builds on the Digital Twin Infrastructure (Task 2.2) and the AI forecasting and orchestration environment developed in WP2, extending them with a decision-support component that assists end-users in understanding, planning, and optimising their energy consumption. In line with EU-DREAM’s user-centric approach, the AI assistant combines short-term forecasting, device-level optimisation, and natural-language interaction to enhance energy awareness, improve accessibility, and increase engagement within the Living Labs.

The assistant is structured into two main modules:

- A forecasting engine, based on data-efficient machine learning models (LightGBM), which predicts non-programmable demand and local renewable generation (PV and wind) with a specific time step and time horizon.
- An optimisation module that generates operating strategies to reduce costs and maximise self-consumption for controllable devices, including EV smart charging, home batteries, coordination devices, and flexible loads. The model is formulated as a linear optimisation problem with penalty-based soft constraints, ensuring computational tractability without the need for commercial solvers.

The deliverable also introduces the device coordination framework, distinguishing between No-Coordination, Coordination, and Smart Coordination Devices. This taxonomy enables the system to model household behaviour while realistically quantifying the actual optimisation potential. Experimental simulations comparing Uncoordinated, Unidirectional, and Bidirectional strategies show consistent improvements in terms of cost reduction and increased self-consumption.

A key innovation of Task 2.3 lies in its integration with the Digital Twin Orchestrator, enabling automated workflows in which forecasting, simulations, optimisation processes, and user interactions are interconnected. The AI assistant receives operational data from the Data Handler, executes forecasting and optimisation tasks, and returns recommendations to the Natural Language Interface (Task 2.4), which translates them into clear, accessible messages for end-users.

During the design phase, LINKS collaborated closely with WP6 to ensure complete alignment with user needs, literacy levels, and behavioural patterns. Insights from surveys, co-design activities, and Living Lab feedback were incorporated into the assistant’s logic, communication style, and optimisation criteria.

Overall, this deliverable defines the architecture, models, and operational logic of the AI-based assistant tool that will support citizens in making informed energy decisions. It lays out the groundwork for an intelligent, transparent, explainable, and user-oriented service that will be validated and demonstrated across the EU-DREAM Living Labs.

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1. Introduction

This document presents an overview of the AI-based Assistant Tool developed within Task 2.3 of the EU-DREAM project. Building upon the Digital Twin Core Infrastructure implemented in Task 2.2 and the modelling foundations introduced in Task 2.1, this task aims to design and implement the AI-driven layer responsible for forecasting, optimisation, and user-oriented decision support. Its purpose is to provide end-users with actionable insights and personalised recommendations to improve energy efficiency, self-consumption, and engagement within the EU-DREAM ecosystem.

Task 2.3 contributes directly to the project's overarching objective of creating a consumer-centric, transparent, and accessible digital energy framework, for instance, by showing and explaining how the different results produced by the algorithm will improve the user's consumption and costs, capable of transforming complex technical processes into intuitive and meaningful services for households and communities. The work performed in this task translates the Digital Twin environment's data flows, simulations, and orchestration capabilities into tangible operational outputs that support everyday energy decisions.

The scope of Task 2.3 includes the development of two core AI components:

- **A short-term forecasting module**, capable of predicting non-programmable demand and renewable generation (solar PV and wind) with a 15-minute resolution up to 36 hours ahead;
- **A linear optimisation engine** that produces cost-optimal, self-consumption-oriented schedules for controllable devices such as EV chargers, home batteries, and coordination-driven appliances.

These modules operate as independent yet interoperable building blocks, exposed to end users through the natural-language interface developed in Task 2.4. This architecture ensures modularity, transparency, and the ability to adapt the assistant to the diverse configurations of the Living Labs.

To ensure alignment with real user needs, Task 2.3 was developed in close collaboration with WP6, integrating survey insights, co-design activities, and feedback from Living Labs into the assistant's logic, communication style, and optimisation objectives. This human-in-the-loop philosophy ensures that the assistant is not merely a technical component but a bridge between EU-DREAM's digital backbone and its citizen-oriented mission.

The document begins with a description of the assistant's role within the project's user-centric vision and the contributions of WP6 to its design. It then presents the two-part AI model structure, followed by a detailed overview of the forecasting module and optimisation engine, including methodology, evaluation, and experimental results. The final sections highlight how the AI assistant integrates with the digital twin ecosystem and provide examples of forecasting, optimisation, and user feedback loops enabled by the orchestrator.

1.1 Project Overview

The EU-DREAM project aims to make the energy system more secure, transparent, and consumer-friendly by combining blockchain technology, DTs, and AI through natural language. Its ambition is to help people and communities use energy more efficiently.

The project works on several fronts: establishing a secure foundation for data integrity and trust through blockchain, developing DT technology to enable real-time simulations and optimisations, and using AI to forecast consumption, optimise usage, and provide tailored recommendations. At the same time, it supports consumer participation in local energy markets by enabling communities to trade surplus energy, shift demand, and engage with energy services transparently and equitably. Finally, EU-DREAM validates its solutions in real-world Living Labs across Europe, demonstrating practical benefits and scalability. Through these efforts, the project seeks to empower consumers, strengthen energy resilience, and accelerate the transition towards a decentralised and sustainable European energy system.

1.2 Task Interconnections

Task 2.3 builds upon the models, tools, and infrastructure developed in the previous tasks of WP2. Specifically, it interacts closely with the Digital Twin models produced under Task 2.1, which replicate the appliances, renewable systems, and household dynamics of the Living Labs. Through the Digital Twin Orchestrator and the data management components implemented in Task 2.2, the AI-based assistant accesses real-time and simulated data streams for forecasting and optimisation. The outcomes generated by the assistant tool are then transmitted to the NLP-based intermediary developed in Task 2.4, which translates AI insights into natural, user-friendly communication.

Together, these components form a cohesive workflow in which data flow, decision-making, and user interaction are integrated into a unified digital framework that connects WP2 to the downstream consumer applications in WP4. Such interconnections are shown in detail in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Relation Between Tasks of WP2, WP3 And WP4

2. Enhancing Energy and Digital Literacy

2.1 Positioning within the User-Centric Objective

Within the EU-DREAM framework, Task 2.3 occupies a pivotal position in connecting the project's technical innovation with its human dimension. One of the project's central ambitions, as stated in the Grant Agreement, *"EU-DREAM aims to improve customers' awareness, trust and confidence in their interactions with the energy market by introducing a smart intermediary – an energy attorney – for end-users."* Our work directly contributes to this vision by developing an AI-based assistant that transforms complex forecasting and optimisation processes into understandable, actionable insights for the end user.

From the early design stages, the LINKS team approached this task not only as a technical challenge but also as a trust-building exercise. The assistant was designed to help users understand why confident energy choices are recommended and what objectives the system is pursuing, whether cost reduction, CO₂ impact, or comfort improvement. This transparency-oriented approach was considered crucial to ensure that users perceive the AI as a helpful and reliable partner rather than a black-box decision-maker.

In this sense, Task 2.3 stands at the crossroads between technology and user empowerment. It aims to turn automation into awareness and optimisation into understanding. By doing so, it bridges the gap between algorithmic intelligence and human perception, helping citizens engage confidently with digital energy tools and actively participate in the just energy transition promoted by EU-DREAM.

2.2 User Feedback and Co-Design

To ensure that the AI-based assistant developed in Task 2.3 remains aligned with real user needs and motivations, LINKS established a structured collaboration with WP6 – *Social Innovation, Consumers' Digital Empowerment and Energy Literacy*. WP6's mandate is to facilitate citizens' participation and increase digital empowerment and energy literacy through co-creation in Living Labs, with specific attention to vulnerable groups and the digital divide. This remit is central to EU-DREAM's impact pathway and explicitly foreseen in WP6 objectives and tasks.

During the initial design of our module, we prioritised end-user goals, typically focused on cost reduction and local renewable self-consumption. To validate these assumptions and ground them in household evidence, LINKS contributed to the content and planning of the EU-DREAM survey under Task 6.2 – *Energy Literacy Empowerment by Co-Creation of Innovative Digital Tools*. Task 6.2 aims to tailor UI options and training materials to users' current literacy level, including experiments with gamification, social features, AI-controlled demand response (DR), and a Natural Language Processing (NLP) interface to enhance engagement and motivation.

The survey explores energy and digital literacy, as well as motivations/barriers, using practical, decision-oriented items. Examples include: *"Which energy-related decisions would you like to make better with more information?"* (e.g. reduce bills, increase comfort, reduce emissions, change supplier, program appliances) and *"Are there barriers that prevent you from making different energy choices today?"* (e.g. complex language, difficult access to data, low trust, no incentive). These items provide a direct window on users' priorities, perceived frictions, and desired features. Furthermore, the questionnaire explicitly addresses confidence and capabilities in

energy and digital actions (e.g., understanding energy bills, identifying high-consumption devices, and comfort with using digital tools for energy tasks). *Figure 2* and *Figure 3* show the format of the example questions in the survey.

Which energy-related topics are you most interested in learning more about?

- Energy use & how to reduce it
- Costs and tariffs
- Environmental impacts
- Supplier comparison
- Comfort/indoor air quality
- Other

Figure 2 - Energy Topic Interests' Survey Question

Are there barriers that prevent you from making different energy choices today?

- Complex language
- Difficult access to data
- Lack of time
- Lack of interest
- Low trust
- Too tired
- No incentive
- No barriers
- Other

Figure 3 - Energy Barriers Survey Question

The LINKS team's contribution was present in the planning of the survey content, ensuring that the questionnaire mirrors the operational logic of the AI assistant (e.g., trade-offs among cost, emissions, comfort; readiness for automation; preferred features). This collaboration guarantees traceability between the assistant's objective functions and validated user preferences gathered from LL participants, consistent with WP6's methodology. The results of this data collection using the survey methodology will be presented and explained in deliverable D6.1.

In parallel, LINKS engaged in a dedicated exchange with the VITO team, responsible for the Belgian Living Lab in Genk, which focuses on social housing and citizen engagement activities. Since the community workshops planned under WP6 will take place later in the project, VITO provided qualitative feedback based on its previous experience engaging tenants in social housing environments.

This collaboration offered valuable insights into the actual level of energy and digital literacy among residents, the communication barriers they face, and their perception of energy-related topics. The collected feedback confirms several of the assumptions underpinning the AI assistant's design:

Residents tend to think in terms of monthly costs rather than kWh, often struggle with digital tools or technical terminology, and show greater motivation toward cost reduction and comfort improvement than toward environmental performance. Furthermore, language barriers, limited internet access, and low trust in automated systems emerged as key constraints to consider when designing user interfaces and recommendation mechanisms.

These findings will serve as reference inputs during the calibration and validation phases of the assistant module. They will help adjust both the communication logic (e.g., language simplification, prioritising cost-related feedback) and the model configuration (e.g., weighting comfort and cost in the optimisation objectives) to ensure the tool remains meaningful and accessible for users with varying degrees of digital literacy and engagement.

The insights emerging from the WP6 survey and other project feedback loops will be used to add fine-tuning capabilities, ensuring that the assistant's capabilities are increasingly aligned with end-users' actual needs and priorities. A practical example grounded in WP6 findings could be the implementation of a small database (or predefined set) of user profiles, each characterised by different optimisation priorities (e.g., cost savings, comfort, CO₂ reduction) and different preferred communication styles. This initial profiling would serve as a starting point for interpreting the end-user type and tailoring the assistant's behaviour accordingly.

A different approach could be to avoid assigning predefined user profiles directly to individuals and instead use the WP6 profiles as reference patterns that capture the most common constraints, priorities, and communication preferences observed across the Living Labs. These patterns can serve as conceptual templates for the NLP module, helping it more easily recognise and interpret user intentions and preferences as they emerge during fundamental interactions.

In this way, user adaptation is not imposed a priori, but progressively inferred through dialogue, while still benefiting from the structured insights collected in WP6. This approach is entirely consistent with EU-DREAM's Specific Objectives, in which WP2/WP6 jointly contribute to enhancing digital energy literacy and user empowerment (SO2/SO9) and to strengthening user engagement across LLs.

3. AI Model Structure

3.1 The Two-Parts Model Logic

The AI-based assistant developed in Task 2.3 is built around two core functionalities that emerged as the most relevant for supporting household energy management in the EU-DREAM Living Labs:

1. Short-term forecasting of household energy behaviour – including non-programmable consumption and local renewable generation (solar PV and wind) over a variable horizon.
2. Optimisation of controllable loads – producing operational recommendations and scheduling proposals for appliances selected by the user as flexible or programmable.

To ensure robustness, transparency, and ease of integration within the EU-DREAM architecture, these two capabilities were implemented as independent yet interoperable modules rather than a single monolithic system.

This architectural choice facilitates adaptation to different Living Lab configurations and future system evolution. Each module can be improved or extended individually as additional data, requirements, or user needs emerge during the project.

The assistant also incorporates the configuration and recommendation logic foreseen for the “AI configuration procurement” functionality. Rather than being implemented as a separate software layer, this functionality is embedded within the optimisation workflow and its interaction with the surrounding system. The optimisation module already produces actionable configuration outputs, such as appliance activation schedules, setpoints, or recommended operating windows, which constitute the concrete guidance required for household energy management.

These outputs form the basis of the configuration service, while the Digital Twin Orchestrator and the NLP interface handle their routing and translation into user-facing recommendations.

3.2 Modularity and Integration

The separation between forecasting and optimisation aligns with the structure of the Digital Twin Core Orchestrator developed in Task 2.2 and described in Deliverable D2.2.

The orchestrator can invoke each module independently, depending on the context and the nature of the request:

- When only future demand or renewable production is required, the orchestrator triggers only the forecasting module.
- When the user requests operational advice (e.g., optimal timing for EV charging), the orchestrator triggers a combined workflow consisting of forecasting followed by optimisation.
- When alternative forecast data are available from other sources, the orchestrator may activate only the optimisation module and provide it with external inputs.

Both modules communicate exclusively through the orchestrator, which ensures controlled data exchange, traceability, and reproducibility across Living Labs.

Forecasting module

The forecasting component provides short-term predictions for all energy quantities that are not directly schedulable and strongly influence optimisation results.

Specifically, it produces predictions for:

- non-coordinable household consumption,
- local PV generation,
- local wind generation (when applicable).

These forecasts constitute the operational baseline used by the optimisation routines.

Optimisation module

Using the forecasts as input, the optimisation component generates recommendations for the operation of controllable devices identified by the user.

The optimisation logic, detailed in the following section 5 The optimisation model, determines the most cost- and energy-efficient scheduling strategies while respecting user-defined constraints and preferences.

4. The Forecasting Model

4.1 Overview and Objectives

Within the EU-DREAM architecture, the forecasting module represents the first step of the AI-based energy management chain. Such forecasting accuracy is essential for the assistant service, as reliable short-term predictions form the basis for meaningful user configurations and strengthen users' trust in the AI-driven recommendations. It is responsible for predicting key variables that feed the optimisation phase, during which a schedule for coordination devices is generated. The forecasts provide the baseline scenario for no-coordination loads and local renewable production, which are the two fundamental sides of the energy balance.

Forecasts are generated at 15-minute resolution with a prediction horizon of up to 36 hours. While both parameters are configurable within the system, these values were selected for the present study as a representative baseline, consistent with the expected LL metering resolution and with typical day-ahead operational planning requirements. These parameters may later be adjusted as more field data becomes available during deployment and testing.

The three forecasting components are defined as:

1. **Electrical demand forecasting** – addressing non-coordinable consumption across the Living Labs.
2. **Solar photovoltaic (PV) generation forecasting** – targeting sites equipped with rooftop or small-scale solar assets.
3. **Wind generation forecasting** – foreseen for Living Labs or replication sites where small wind production is available.

To achieve these goals, the module relies on a combination of historical measurements and external data streams, whose specific content depends on the availability within each Living Lab:

- Historical **energy consumption** data for the zones or buildings under analysis.
- **Meteorological data** (irradiance, temperature, wind speed, cloud coverage) are used as exogenous features for renewable generation forecasting.
- Historical **production data** were available to calibrate local PV or wind generation models.
- **Temporal indicators** (hour of day, weekday, season) to capture periodic patterns.

This data foundation enables the forecasting module to operate consistently across diverse Living Lab contexts, from sites with rich monitoring infrastructure to those with limited sensing capacity, while maintaining sufficient accuracy for downstream optimisation. In the following sections, the design and implementation of the three forecasting models (load, solar and wind) are presented in detail.

4.2 Forecasting of Electrical Demand

The load forecasting sub-module focuses on predicting the consumption patterns of non-coordinable devices, i.e., all electrical loads that will not be directly scheduled or optimised by the AI assistant.

While controllable appliances, such as EV charging points, washing machines, dishwashers, and HVAC/heat pumps, will be managed through the optimisation engine, the remaining background loads (lighting, electronics, base demand, etc.) must be forecast to anticipate the overall energy demand profile for each Living Lab.

Depending on the configuration defined by each user and site, the share of non-controllable consumption may vary. Hence, an easy, flexible forecasting mechanism was designed to adapt to varying levels of controllability across the Living Labs. The only data needed for load forecasting were expected to be the previous overall non-schedulable consumption and the timestamps of those measures.

4.2.1 Data selection and modelling approach

To identify the most suitable AI algorithm for this forecasting task, publicly available historical load datasets were collected from online repositories (open smart-meter data) to simulate the conditions expected in the Living Labs.

The datasets used for prototyping and comparing forecasting models were obtained from the Open Power System Data (OPSD) platform (Wiese, et al., 2019), a free-of-charge data service for electricity system researchers. OPSD collects, checks, processes, documents, and publishes energy data that is publicly available but otherwise difficult to access and use efficiently.

The platform provides a well-documented, internally consistent time series of electricity consumption, spot prices, and renewable generation (wind and solar) across European countries. All data are openly accessible, version-controlled, and published under permissive licenses to support reproducible and transparent energy system modelling.

The selected models were chosen to balance three key aspects:

- **Prediction accuracy** on unseen data;
- **Computational cost** (training time and inference latency);
- **Robustness to limited and incomplete datasets**, as not all Living Labs would have long or fully structured time series.

Different model families were considered:

- **Multi-Output Linear Regression (MOLR)** – a transparent and straightforward baseline model capable of producing multi-step forecasts simultaneously, though limited in representing non-linear relationships;
- **Decision Tree (DT)** – a tree-based method that recursively partitions the data to capture simple non-linear dependencies while maintaining interpretability;
- **Random Forest (RF)** – an ensemble of multiple decision trees that improves robustness to noise and variance through aggregation;

- **Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM)** – a gradient-boosted decision tree model optimised for efficiency on tabular datasets and tolerant to missing or irregular data;
- **Long Short-Term Memory network (LSTM)** – a recurrent neural architecture designed to capture sequential and temporal dependencies, but generally more data- and computation-intensive.

4.2.2 Evaluation methodology

The forecasting module was purposely designed to remain usable and reliable even under data-scarce conditions, enabling all Living Labs, including those not yet fully instrumented or operational, to leverage its predictive capabilities and obtain preliminary insights from the earliest stages of deployment.

To emulate such conditions, different families of models were tested using a six-month historical subset of the Open Power System Data (OPSD) dataset. Each model was trained on a rolling 6-month window and evaluated on the subsequent month, using a rolling-origin validation scheme to ensure comparability and robustness of the results. The split between the training and test sets was set to 85% and 15%, respectively.

A 15-minute timestamp resolution was selected for the evaluation, as it provided the best trade-off between forecast accuracy and temporal granularity.

The evaluation metrics adopted were:

- **MAE (Mean Absolute Error)** – measures the average magnitude of prediction errors, providing a direct interpretation in the same units as the data (kWh).
- **RMSE (Root Mean Square Error)** – penalises larger deviations more strongly, giving insight into the model's stability against peaks and sudden variations and making it the most suitable parameter for load studies.

These two metrics were selected because they offer a balanced view of accuracy and consistency and are widely used in energy forecasting literature.

4.2.3 Feature Engineering

A dedicated feature engineering strategy was developed to capture temporal dynamics, historical dependencies, and nonlinear relationships in household energy consumption data. The goal was to create a robust, data-efficient feature set that could enhance model performance even in limited-data scenarios.

In total, 26 engineered features were implemented, grouped into five main categories as illustrated below. Each group targets a specific temporal or behavioural dimension of energy use, ensuring that both short-term fluctuations and long-term patterns are represented within the model input space.

Temporal Features (4 features)

These features encode time-dependent behavioural patterns, ensuring the model can differentiate between weekdays, weekends, and working hours (*Table 1*).

To preserve the cyclical nature of time, sine and cosine transformations are used to prevent discontinuities between consecutive days (e.g., 23:45 and 00:15).

Feature	Description	Calculation	Rationale
hour_sin	Hour of day (sine)	$\sin(2\pi \times (\text{hour} + \text{min}/60) / 24)$	Smooth 24h cycle encoding
hour_cos	Hour of day (cosine)	$\cos(2\pi \times (\text{hour} + \text{min}/60) / 24)$	Avoids discontinuity at midnight
is_weekend	Weekend flag	1 if Sat/Sun, 0 otherwise	Distinguish leisure vs workday load
is_business_hours	Business hours flag	1 if Mon–Fri 08:00–18:00	Work-related consumption patterns
month_sin	Month of the year (sin)	$\sin(2\pi \times (\text{month}) / 12)$	Preserve annual seasonality in a continuous, cyclical form
month_cos	Month of the year (cos)	$\cos(2\pi \times (\text{month}) / 12)$	Avoid artificial jumps between December and January; capture annual seasonality.

Table 1 - Temporal Features List

Lag Features (6 features)

Lag features represent past consumption values at different time offsets. They capture autocorrelation and short-term inertia typical of household energy usage (*Table 2*).

Feature	Time Offset	Rationale
lag_1	15 minutes ago	Captures immediate consumption dependency
lag_2	30 minutes ago	Identifies short-term patterns
lag_4	1 hour ago	Detects hourly periodicity
lag_6	1.5 hours ago	Captures extended short-term behaviour
lag_12	3 hours ago	Mid-term dependency
lag_24	6 hours ago	Represents the same time in the prior cycle

Table 2 - Lag Features List

Difference Features (3 features)

Difference features measure the rate of change over time, enabling the model to detect rising or falling consumption trends while avoiding data leakage (*Table 3*).

Feature	Description	Calculation	Purpose
diff_1	15-min change	$\text{lag}_1[t-1] - \text{lag}_1[t-2]$	Captures consumption momentum

diff_4	1-hour change	$lag_1[t-1] - lag_1[t-5]$	Detects hourly trends
diff_12	3-hour change	$lag_1[t-1] - lag_1[t-13]$	Measures medium-term variations

Table 3 - Difference Features List

Ratio Features (5 features)

These features compute relationships between time scales, making the model scale-invariant and sensitive to relative changes rather than absolute values (*Table 4*).

Feature	Calculation	Interpretation
ratio_short_long	$rolling_mean_4 / rolling_mean_48$	Compares recent vs long-term trend
ratio_recent_daily	$lag_1 / rolling_mean_48$	Current vs daily average
volatility_ratio	$rolling_std_4 / rolling_std_24$	Short vs medium volatility
ratio_current_min24	$lag_1 / rolling_min_24$	Position vs 24h minimum
ratio_current_max24	$lag_1 / rolling_max_24$	Position vs 24h maximum

Table 4 - Ratio Features List

Interaction Features (6 features)

Interaction terms model non-linear dependencies and contextual effects, combining temporal and statistical signals (*Table 5*).

Feature	Components	Purpose
lag_1_x_hour_sin	Recent consumption × Time-of-day	Detects hour-dependent behaviour
lag_1_x_hour_cos	Recent consumption × Time-of-day	Captures the complementary time effect
rolling_mean_24_x_is_weekend	6h average × Weekend flag	Weekend-specific consumption
rolling_mean_12_x_is_business_hours	3h average × Business hours	Workday context integration
rolling_std_4_x_hour_sin	Short-term variability × Time	Temporal volatility effect
ratio_short_long_x_is_weekend	Trend ratio × Weekend	Behavioural shift on weekends

Table 5 - Interaction Features List

The final feature matrix combines short-, medium-, and long-term indicators, balancing interpretability and predictive power.

Data Gaps Handling

Energy consumption datasets often contain missing timestamps due to sensor failures or maintenance. The approach used is:

1. Fill gaps with NaN to maintain temporal continuity
2. Compute features for every timestamp, allowing NaN to propagate through lag features
3. Remove all rows containing any NaN values from the feature matrix to ensure data integrity and prevent artificial patterns introduced by imputation.

This conservative strategy prioritises data quality: since lag features fundamentally depend on historical data, no imputation method can reliably reconstruct missing consumption values. Removing incomplete rows ensures that all features are derived from real historical data, eliminating statistical artefacts that could compromise forecasting accuracy.

An example of a 6-hour data gap is presented in Table 6, and this gap continues to affect the feature matrix for six additional hours after data resumes, because lag₂₄ depends on information 6 hours earlier.

Timestamp	Load	lag_1	lag_4	lag_24	Status	Action
00:00	45.2	46.3	47.1	47.5	All features valid	Keep
00:15	44.8	45.2	46.3	47.1	All features valid	Keep
00:30	NaN	44.8	45.2	46.3	Gap begins	Remove
01:00	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN propagates	Remove
06:00	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	Deep lags affected	Remove
06:30	48.1	NaN	NaN	45.2	lag_1 and lag_4 still NaN	Remove
07:00	49.2	47.9	48.1	NaN	lag_24 still NaN (6h gap)	Remove
07:30	48.5	48.8	49.2	48.1	All features valid	Keep

Table 6 – Example Of Data Gaps Handling

4.2.4 Hyperparameter Tuning with Optuna

Hyperparameter tuning was conducted using Optuna, an advanced open-source framework for automated parameter optimisation (Akiba, Sano, Yanase, Ohta, & Koyama, 2019).

The search used a Tree-structured Parzen Estimator (TPE) algorithm with Bayesian optimisation to minimise Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) on a validation subset.

Hyperparameter tuning was conducted using Optuna, an advanced open-source framework for automated parameter optimisation (Akiba, Sano, Yanase, Ohta, & Koyama, 2019). To ensure generalisation, each model underwent cross-validation with early stopping to prevent overfitting.

Between 50 and 100 optimisation trials were performed per model, balancing search depth and computational efficiency.

4.2.5 Optimized Configurations

LightGBM achieved the most stable and accurate performance. The best configuration included a *learning rate* of 0.05, 31 *leaves*, and a *feature fraction* of 0.9, providing a conservative yet efficient balance between bias and variance.

Regularisation was introduced via bagging (80%) and feature subsampling, ensuring robustness across data variations.

MultiOutputLinearRegression was optimised using Ridge regularisation ($\alpha=1.0$) with a closed-form solver, yielding a computationally efficient baseline.

The optimal Random Forest used 50 *estimators* with a *maximum depth* of 5, balancing interpretability and accuracy. Using square-root feature sampling ($\text{max features}=\text{'sqrt'}$) ensured model diversity while avoiding overfitting on small datasets.

For the Decision Tree, a shallow *max depth* of 5 was found to perform best, confirming that a simple tree acts as an effective baseline for ensemble methods.

The tuned LSTM used a single *recurrent layer* (32 units) with tanh *activation*, Adam *optimiser*, and RMSE loss.

The network was trained for five epochs with early stopping and a batch size of 300, balancing training stability and computational cost.

4.2.6 Results and discussion

The results in *Table 7* highlight that LightGBM achieved the best trade-off between forecasting accuracy and data efficiency.

Model	MAE	RMSE
LightGBM	0.0508	0.0775
Multi-Output Linear Regression	0.0511	0.0796
Random Forest	0.0530	0.0781
Decision Tree	0.0550	0.0819
LSTM	0.0636	0.0897

Table 7 - Forecasting Performance Comparison

This finding is consistent with recent literature, which highlights LightGBM's ability to compete with, and even outperform, complex deep learning architectures on tabular energy data. For instance, Shiblee & Koukaras conducted a comparative study of power distribution systems, demonstrating that LightGBM achieved better accuracy metrics (RMSE and MAE) than STM and CNN models while requiring a fraction of the computational resources (Shiblee & Koukaras, 2025). Such evidence supports our design choice to adopt LightGBM as the default forecasting algorithm, ensuring high performance without the extensive hardware requirements typically associated with deep neural networks.

4.2.7 Overview of LightGBM

Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) is a gradient boosting framework based on decision trees, designed to deliver high predictive accuracy while maintaining computational efficiency (Ke, et al., 2017). It belongs to the family of ensemble learning methods, in which a sequence of weak learners (typically shallow decision trees) is iteratively trained to correct the residual errors from previous iterations.

The key strength of LightGBM lies in its leaf-wise tree growth strategy, which expands the tree by always splitting the leaf that leads to the most significant reduction in loss. This results in models that capture complex nonlinear relationships more effectively than traditional level-wise boosting methods, particularly when dealing with tabular data characterised by a mix of temporal, lag-based and statistical features, as in the EU-DREAM forecasting task.

In addition to its modelling capabilities, LightGBM offers several practical advantages that address the constraints of the Living Labs. It is computationally lightweight, enabling rapid training even on modest hardware—an important property during iterative calibration and testing phases. It also provides robust handling of missing values, which avoids the need for imputation strategies that could introduce artefacts into the time series.

Furthermore, LightGBM performs well even with limited historical data, thanks to its ability to extract informative patterns from engineered features rather than relying on long sequential histories. This characteristic distinguishes it from deep learning models such as LSTMs, which typically require longer, denser time series to reach their full potential.

An example of the LightGBM forecast is shown in Figure 4; the plot shows some error but captures the overall trend of the actual values.

Figure 4 - LightGBM Load Prediction Vs Actual Values

4.3 Forecasting of Solar Generation

The photovoltaic (PV) forecasting component aims to predict short-term renewable generation within the Living Labs, focusing on solar energy as the most widely deployed, flexible and scalable green source for small-scale environments.

Understanding expected PV production over the next few hours is essential to align consumption with local generation availability, thereby increasing self-consumption and reducing grid dependency.

4.3.1 Data selection and modelling approach

The model was trained and validated using hourly production data collected from the Italian Living Lab (LL3), comprising 8,352 power production records over roughly one year of operation.

These data represent the site's actual PV generation, providing a realistic baseline for model development and calibration.

To complement these historical measurements, meteorological variables (solar irradiance, temperature, and cloud coverage) were obtained from the Open-Meteo API, an open-access and highly reliable source of global weather forecasts.

To forecast renewable generation, a LightGBM-based regression model was developed. The model was trained using historical Open-Meteo forecasts (irradiance, temperature, cloud cover) as input features and the measured PV production from LL3 as the target variable. This approach enables the model to learn the relationship between forecast meteorological conditions and actual energy output, producing accurate, computationally lightweight predictions.

LightGBM was selected due to its ability to:

- perform well with limited datasets;
- handle missing values and non-linear relationships;
- train rapidly with minimal computational resources.

During inference, the trained model receives real-time weather forecasts from the Open-Meteo API and predicts PV generation at each hourly time step, supporting operational scheduling and optimisation decisions.

The model trained achieved good results in terms of error metrics, with a MAE of 0.062 kW (1.2% of the 5 kWp system capacity) and a RMSE of 0.0838 kW.

Figure 5 and *Figure 6* illustrate examples of predicted versus actual photovoltaic production at different points of the test set. The results show that, while forecasts are generally accurate

under typical conditions, some days exhibit higher variability and reduced predictability. Nevertheless, the overall error remains within an acceptable and manageable range.

Figure 5 - LightGBM Solar Prediction Vs Actual Values Example 1

Figure 6 - LightGBM Solar Prediction Vs Actual Values Example 2

The second plot highlights a recurring error where the model assigns small negative or non-zero production values during night hours (red circles). To mitigate this issue, a post-processing step is applied to set all predictions to 0 kW when solar irradiance equals zero, effectively correcting these unrealistic outputs.

The model-predicted power is then interpolated linearly to 15-minute granularity and converted to energy production for that timestep.

4.4 Forecasting of Wind Generation

Wind energy is the second-most-deployed form of local renewable energy in Living Labs, though its presence is significantly less widespread than that of solar photovoltaic systems. Wind generation is typically implemented through small-scale domestic turbines with moderate power ratings, mounted on building rooftops or nearby structures.

4.4.1 Data selection and modelling approach

Initial efforts to develop a wind forecasting model followed the same machine learning-based methodology successfully employed for solar PV forecasting. Production data from wind turbines was requested from Living Labs already equipped with operational wind generation systems. Specifically, wind production measurements were obtained from Living Lab 6 (LL6) for model training and validation purposes.

However, the collected wind production data proved unsuitable for the correlation-based machine learning approach used with Open-Meteo historical weather data. The primary challenge encountered was the high variability of power output between consecutive time intervals. Unlike solar generation, which exhibits relatively smooth transitions due to the predictable solar geometry and gradual cloud movements, wind power demonstrated rapid fluctuations driven by turbulent wind patterns, local microclimatic effects, and turbine control dynamics. This high-frequency variability made it difficult to establish stable correlations between historical meteorological variables and measured production, leading to poor model generalisation.

Given the limitations of the data-driven approach with the available measurements, a more theoretical and physics-based methodology was adopted for this initial implementation phase. Rather than learning patterns from historical production data, the wind forecasting model relies solely on

1. **Wind speed forecasts** from the Open-Meteo weather service
2. **Turbine nameplate specifications** (technical parameters from manufacturer datasheets)

This approach eliminates the dependency on site-specific historical measurements and instead uses well-established empirical relationships to estimate power production.

4.4.2 Turbine Technical Parameters

The forecasting model requires the following turbine specifications, which are configured for each Living Lab in the system configuration files:

- **rated_power_kw** – Nominal (rated) power capacity of the turbine, expressed in kilowatts (kW); represents the maximum power output under optimal wind conditions.
- **cut_in_speed** – Minimum wind speed (m/s) required for the turbine to start generating electricity (typically around 3.5 m/s).
- **rated_speed** – Wind speed (m/s) at which the turbine reaches its rated power output (commonly around 12.0 m/s).
- **cut_out_speed** – Maximum wind speed (m/s) at which the turbine automatically shuts down for safety reasons (usually near 25.0 m/s).

- **hub_height** – Height of the turbine hub above ground level (m); for small wind installations, this is often around 10 m.
- **reference_height** – Height (m) at which the meteorological wind speed data are provided (typically 10 m for Open-Meteo datasets).
- **shear_exponent** – Wind shear coefficient (default = 0.143 for urban context), used to extrapolate wind speed from the reference height to the turbine hub height.

These parameters fully characterise the turbine's power production behaviour and enable physics-based forecasting without historical training data.

4.4.3 Power Calculation Functions

The wind production forecasting model implements two core computational functions.

Wind Shear Correction

This function adjusts the wind speed from the meteorological reference height (typically 10 m, as provided by Open-Meteo) to the turbine hub height, using the power-law wind profile. Wind speed increases with height above ground due to reduced surface friction. Estimating the correct hub-height wind speed is crucial, as turbine power output is sensitive to even slight variations in wind speed.

The correction follows the classical power law relationship:

$$v(h_2) = v(h_1) \times \left(\frac{h_2}{h_1}\right)^\alpha$$

Where:

- $v(h_1)$ = wind speed at reference height (m/s)
- $v(h_2)$ = wind speed at hub height (m/s)
- h_1 = reference height (e.g. 10 m)
- h_2 = turbine hub height (m)
- α = wind shear exponent, typically 0.143 for urban areas

This correction ensures that subsequent power calculations are based on realistic wind conditions at the actual turbine elevation.

Theoretical Power Curve

This function estimates the turbine's electrical power output based on the corrected hub-height wind speed, using a four-region power curve model commonly used in wind energy analysis (Saint-Drenan, et al., 2020).

Region 1 – Below Cut-In ($v < v_{cut_in}$)

- $P = 0\text{kW}$
- The turbine remains idle at low wind speeds to prevent mechanical wear and inefficient operation.

Region 2 – Cubic Ramp ($v_{cut_in} \leq v < v_{rated}$)

- Power increases cubically with wind speed between the cut-in and rated thresholds.
- The relationship is expressed as:

$$P = P_{rated} \times \left(\frac{v - v_{cut_in}}{v_{rated} - v_{cut_in}} \right)^3$$

- This follows the theoretical proportionality $P \propto v^3$ derived from the kinetic energy of moving air.

Region 3 – Rated Power ($v_{rated} \leq v < v_{cut_out}$)

- $P = P_{rated}$ (constant at maximum capacity)
- The turbine’s control system adjusts blade pitch to maintain constant output and avoid overload.

Region 4 – Cut-Out Shutdown ($v \geq v_{cut_out}$)

- $P = 0kW$
- The turbine automatically shuts down under extreme wind conditions to prevent structural damage.

This simplified empirical model captures the non-linear relationship between wind speed and electrical power generation without requiring manufacturer-specific data. Although it is a first-order approximation, it provides a robust, generalizable approach for forecasting turbine output based solely on meteorological information. The approach is visually explained in *Figure 7*.

Figure 7 - Wind Turbine Theoretical Power Curve

Figure 8 illustrates a representative 36-hour wind production forecast generated by the theoretical power curve model for a 5 kW domestic turbine. The forecast demonstrates the characteristic high variability inherent to wind energy generation, with significant power fluctuations occurring over short time intervals due to changing meteorological conditions.

The upper panel displays the predicted wind speed evolution, showing both favourable and low-wind periods. The lower panel translates these wind patterns into electrical power output via the cubic power curve, revealing peak production exceeding 4 kW during high-wind events and near-zero generation during calm periods.

Figure 8 - Wind Production Forecast

5. Optimisation Model

5.1 Overview and Objective

The goal is to reduce the user's energy consumption and costs.

In a typical household, the system variables correspond to the set of electrical devices installed and used within the domestic environment. For this reason, a classification of these devices was carried out to understand better how to define the problem.

Three important input dimensions were identified: costs, consumption, and generation, each further divided into more specific categories.

The objective is now to analyse the energy consumption of an average user in their home and to understand how this can be optimised through an algorithm integrated into the Energy Management System (EMS).

5.2 Problem Characterization

As previously mentioned, three important input dimensions were initially identified:

Costs:

Having accurate knowledge of this information is essential to achieve the system's objective.

In many European countries, time-of-use (ToU) pricing schemes are applied.

ToU tariffs differentiate electricity costs by time of day and day of the week.

In practice, electricity does not always have the same price: there are periods when it is more expensive (peak hours), others when it is cheaper (off-peak hours), and often an intermediate band as well.

This structure is designed to reflect the fundamental dynamics of energy supply and demand. During daytime and working hours, electricity demand is high; therefore, production and grid management costs increase. At night and on weekends, demand decreases, making electricity cheaper.

Time-of-use pricing has two main goals:

- Encouraging more efficient energy use and pushing consumers to shift part of their consumption to cheaper hours, thus reducing grid load peaks.
- Supporting the integration of renewable energy sources, which often produce variably over time, enables a more flexible and stable operation of the electrical system.

Figure 9 - Annual Trend of Italian Energy Consumption

Figure 10 - Average Daily Electricity Consumption in Italy

Figure 9 shows the annual trend in Italian energy consumption, from which the seasonal variation is evident. Specifically, energy demand tends to peak in summer and is lower in winter.

Meanwhile, Figure 10 shows the average daily electricity consumption in Italy. From this curve, the previously discussed ToU pricing schemes are derived and presented in the following Figure 11.

Figure 11 - Daily Energy Price Variation by Time-of-Day Bands

Generation:

Self-generation is essential for achieving the system's objectives. As shown in the previous sections, the two main renewable sources considered in the residential context are photovoltaic (PV) and wind power.

The management of energy storage systems is also crucial. Energy storage is a fundamental element of energy optimisation because it allows production and consumption to be decoupled.

In a traditional electrical system, energy must be consumed at the exact moment it is produced; storage, instead, enables excess energy (e.g., from renewable sources during low-demand periods) to be stored and released during peak hours or when production is insufficient.

This provides several advantages:

- It increases self-consumption of PV systems, reducing dependence on the grid.
- It lowers energy costs by allowing users to purchase electricity when prices are low and use it when prices are higher.
- It supports the integration of renewable sources by mitigating their natural variability.

In summary, storage is key to making energy optimisation truly effective, as it introduces temporal flexibility and enables intelligent, sustainable energy management.

Some of these devices will partially fall within consumption categories.

Consumption:

A household contains a wide variety of devices that must be connected to the electrical grid and, therefore, act as passive loads. The first step in analysing the problem was to group these devices into categories, since predicting the behaviour of every single appliance individually would be highly complex. By creating management logic for each category, any specific appliance can then be classified accordingly, and its control strategy will already be defined.

The categories created are:

1. No-Coordination Devices
2. Coordination Devices
3. Smart Coordination Devices

This distinction reflects the level of automation and integration of each device within the energy management system. It determines the extent to which user behaviour affects the overall effectiveness of the optimisation process.

1. No-Coordination Devices.

No-Coordination Devices represent fully static loads that cannot be managed or optimised by the algorithm.

Their consumption profile is fixed, independent of control logic or external signals, and they do not interact with the EMS.

Examples include refrigerators, lighting systems, and basic electronic devices that operate according to constant, non-modifiable routines.

These elements constitute the system's rigid demand: a constant consumption baseline around which the optimiser must plan the management of flexible resources, without any possibility of intervention or temporal shifting.

2. Coordination Devices

Coordination Devices introduce an initial level of flexibility, but their operation requires direct collaboration between the user and the algorithm.

In this case, the user maintains an active role; they must physically prepare or activate the device (for example, loading the washing machine, selecting a program, or connecting an appliance), implicitly or explicitly signalling to the system that the device is "ready" to operate. Once this availability signal is received, the algorithm optimises the optimal time to start the device based on energy prices, renewable generation, and power constraints. The optimisation does not replace the user; instead, it assists them by automatically planning the optimal operating time.

This category represents semi-automatic coordination; the system can decide when to act, but only after the user has provided input and performed the necessary physical actions. Typical examples include washing machines, dishwashers, and other programmable appliances that require preliminary human interaction.

3. Smart Coordination Devices

Smart Coordination Devices represent the most advanced level, in which user intervention is practically non-existent.

These devices continuously communicate with the algorithm and can manage their operations autonomously, reacting in real time to price signals, renewable generation, and battery state of charge.

Typical examples include battery storage systems, photovoltaic inverters, and smart Wallbox for electric vehicles (EVs), which operate continuously and adaptively, automatically optimising energy flows to meet system objectives without requiring any user action.

In this case, the EMS has direct, bidirectional control over the device, which acts as an intelligent agent within the energy balancing process, capable of modulating power, charging and discharging, and feeding energy into the grid autonomously and in coordination with other resources.

In summary, the classification logic is based not only on the device's technological level but also on its degree of decision-making autonomy and the effort required of the user.

Categories	Intervention by the user	Type of Coordination	Level of automation
No-Coordination	Total	None	None
Coordination	Partial	Semi-Automatic	Medium
Smart Coordination	None	Automatic	High

Table 8 - Device Classification

This classification enables realistic modelling of device behaviour and quantification of the system's optimisation potential, not only based on available technology but also on the level of user involvement, which remains a key factor in the transition toward intelligent and participatory energy management.

5.2.1 Electrical grid characterisation

It is imperative to understand how electrical energy flows are managed within a household.

Figure 12 - Single-Line Diagram

Figure 12 represents the single-line diagram of a household equipped with a photovoltaic system and battery storage.

Meanwhile, Figure 13 shows a simplified diagram of the system.

Figure 13 - System Architecture Diagram

The system shown in the figures above (a PV system is illustrated, but the same logic applies to a wind power system) comprises an integrated set of components that work together to optimise self-consumption and reduce dependence on the electrical grid.

The main elements of the system are:

- Photovoltaic modules (PV strings)
- Photovoltaic inverter (DC/AC)
- Battery storage system
- Wallbox for EV charging
- Household loads (domestic appliances)
- Grid connection via point of delivery (POD)

5.3 Operation of a Non-Optimised Residential Electrical Network

During operation, energy flows dynamically among these elements in response to solar production, instantaneous household demand, and remaining storage capacity.

5.3.1 Flow Management Logic:

1. Photovoltaic generation

PV modules produce direct current (DC) electricity during daylight hours.

The photovoltaic inverter converts this energy into alternating current (AC), which is compatible with the household electrical system and domestic loads. The generated power is immediately routed to the house's active loads (e.g., appliances, lighting, wallbox, etc.).

2. Instant self-consumption

If the power produced is equal to or lower than the household's instantaneous demand, all the energy is consumed locally with no need for grid withdrawal. In this scenario, maximum direct self-consumption is achieved, which is the most economically advantageous form of consumption.

3. Storage of excess energy

If solar production exceeds instantaneous consumption, the surplus energy is directed to the batteries, which begin charging.

The batteries store the energy as DC and, like the PV system, are connected to the installation via an inverter.

When the battery is fully charged, any additional surplus can be fed into the grid, generating a positive contribution to the bidirectional meter.

4. Use of stored energy

When there is no solar production, and the household is actively consuming, the system switches to battery discharge mode.

The stored energy is converted into AC by the inverter and used to supply domestic loads, reducing or avoiding grid withdrawal.

5. EV charging management

When the EV is connected to the wallbox, it will start charging immediately.

6. Interaction with the grid

The bidirectional electricity meter measures both the energy withdrawn from the grid (when consumption exceeds local production) and the energy fed into the grid (when surplus production cannot be self-consumed or stored).

Therefore, a well-configured system follows this priority logic:

1. Supply household loads with PV energy.
2. Charge the batteries when there is surplus production.
3. Feed only the excess energy that cannot be used or stored locally into the grid.
4. Withdraw from the grid only when PV and batteries are insufficient.

5.4 Linear Optimisation Algorithm

Several algorithms were considered, and the Linear Programming (LP) optimisation algorithm was ultimately selected.

LP is a mathematical methodology for minimising or maximising a linear objective function subject to linear constraints.

In an LP model, both the objective function and the constraints are expressed as linear combinations of the decision variables. This makes such problems particularly well-suited for describing energy systems, electrical networks, power flows, and resource allocation.

The advantages of using this approach are:

1. **Guaranteed and deterministic solution**
LP problems always have a deterministic optimal solution (either unique or part of an equivalent optimal set) whenever a feasible region exists.
Unlike nonlinear methods, they do not suffer from local minima.
2. **High computational efficiency**
Solution algorithms (Interior Point, ECOS, OSQP, etc.) have polynomial-time complexity and fast convergence, even for large systems with thousands of variables and constraints.
3. **Numerical robustness**
Linear formulations are stable and less sensitive to data perturbations compared to nonlinear or heuristic methods.
4. **Scalability and modularity**
LP models are easily extendable: adding new constraints or variables (such as additional loads, generators, or storage systems) does not change the nature of the problem or compromise solvability.
5. **Interpretability of the results**
Dual variables (Lagrange multipliers) have a clear physical meaning, making the method transparent and easy to analyse.
6. **Easy integration of realistic constraints**
Capacity limits, energy balance equations, power constraints, and state-of-charge (SoC) dynamics can all be linearised, ensuring a coherent and realistic model without introducing unnecessary complexity.
7. **Suitable for multi-agent or multi-prosumer scenarios**
The matrix-based structure of the problem (variables for each prosumer and each timestep) naturally supports a compact, vectorised linear formulation.

Furthermore, one reason for preferring this type of algorithm over a Machine Learning-based approach is the limited initial availability of data, which would have posed a significant obstacle to training such a model.

The Python library *CVXPY* was used together with the *ECOS* solver.

A 15-minute time step was adopted over a 36-hour time horizon. The 36-hour window provides a sufficiently representative interval for user optimisation. At the same time, the 15-minute

resolution offers a good balance between reactivity and computational effort, ensuring that the system remains responsive without being overloaded.

Before detailing the operation of the developed optimisation algorithm, it is important to clarify that, at this stage, no real-world data have been collected within the scope of this project. As a result, complete and continuous datasets on PV system usage, household loads, and wallbox charging are not currently available from the project labs.

For this reason, synthetic data were generated to design, implement, and test the optimisation algorithm: consumption of configurable household devices, battery behaviour, and EV charging profiles.

These data were modelled based on realistic scenarios, average residential consumption profiles, PV production curves, and standard usage patterns of energy devices.

This phase enabled verification of the algorithm's logical and computational correctness, exploring both its potential and limitations. Once a reliable historical dataset becomes available, the model will be adapted and recalibrated using real data, and validation tests will be conducted on concrete case studies to assess its performance in real-world scenarios and further optimise its parameters.

5.4.1 Difficulty and Structure of the Optimisation Problem

The problem developed in this work falls into the category of Mixed-Integer Linear Programming (MILP) problems, characterised by the simultaneous presence of:

- Continuous variables, such as power flows, state of charge, and energy consumption, can take real values within defined ranges.
- Binary variables are used to model logical decisions (for example, switching loads on/off or choosing between energy import and export).

The coexistence of these two types of variables makes the problem inherently nonconvex and computationally intensive, as the search space grows exponentially with the number of binary variables.

Common open-source convex optimisation libraries, such as CVXPY, do not natively support mixed-integer problems. They are designed for continuous variables with linear or conic constraints, and mixed-integer capabilities are only available through external MIP solvers.

For this reason, a hybrid strategy was adopted to reduce complexity by reformulating certain constraints as soft constraints. These eliminate the need for binary variables, making the algorithm linear and therefore solvable with the chosen framework.

In soft constraints, instead of enforcing a complex condition, a penalty term is added to the objective function that discourages but does not strictly forbid violating the constraint.

For example, constraints such as maintaining the SoC within a given range or prioritising the use of renewable energy are “softened” through penalties proportional to the deviation from the desired value:

$$\text{Min}f(x) = C_{\text{energy}} + \lambda \cdot \text{penalty}$$

where the coefficient λ regulates the severity of the penalty. This formulation enabled keeping the problem linearly solvable using open-source libraries, thus avoiding the need for commercial solvers, though at the cost of greater difficulty in tuning the penalty weights and ensuring numerical stability of the solution. The specific cases will be illustrated below.

5.5 Strategy Cases

5.5.1 Case 1. Uncoordinated Strategy

This algorithm was developed to manage the system in the same way it would be operated today, following the logic described in 5.3.1 Flow Management Logic. The results will be used as a baseline for comparison.

5.5.2 Case 2. Unidirectional Optimization

This strategy is referred to as unidirectional because the electric vehicle is treated as a passive load: it can only absorb energy. It cannot feed it back into the home system. In the next strategy, the vehicle is modelled as an active load, enabling bidirectional power flow. The forecast and optimisation algorithms are connected via an HTTP endpoint. This means that the first operation performed by the optimisation algorithm is to call the forecast model via an HTTP endpoint to obtain the predictions required for computation, specifically the values of household energy generation and consumption. As for consumption, only the No-Coordination devices, that is, the static loads, are considered; their values are obtained by subtracting the consumption associated with Coordination and Smart Coordination devices from the total household consumption.

These data represent the electrical consumption [kWh] with a 15-minute time resolution and are structured as follows:

timestamp	predicted_demand	predicted_production
2025-09-12 15:00:00	0,052324301	0,304312255
2025-09-12 15:15:00	0,074008546	0,278794247
2025-09-12 15:30:00	0,082530257	0,253276239
2025-09-12 15:45:00	0,079817483	0,227758231
2025-09-12 16:00:00	0,105642621	0,202240223

Table 9 - Forecast Data Extrapolations

Table 9 is only a fragment of the .xlsx file, which contains data for the following 36 hours. After this, a table is created to map the ongoing charging events and their corresponding disconnections.

It is assumed that the user can set the arrival and departure times at home, and therefore the EV connection and disconnection times.

An additional table is then created to determine the EV's state of charge at the moment of connection (a value obtained from the wallbox) and the available charging time based on the known disconnection time.

At this point, all required information is available: energy prices, static household consumption, self-generation, battery state of charge, and EV charging availability. From here, the analysis of the optimisation algorithm begins.

The optimisation problem is formulated as a multivariable linear programming model to minimise the overall operating cost of a distributed energy system.

The user can consume, generate, store, and exchange electrical energy with the grid. The optimisation simultaneously coordinates these actions over a discrete time horizon T , ensuring both technical feasibility and economic efficiency.

Let N be the number of time intervals. For a 36-hour horizon with a 15-minute time step, we obtain $N = 144$.

The model considers a set of decision variables for each time instant $t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$:

- uP_t : net energy exchanged with the grid (positive when purchasing energy)
- uN_t : energy fed into the grid;
- PEV_t : EV charging power;
- SoC_t : state of charge of the EV battery;
- $Pbat_t$: power flow of the local stationary battery;
- $SoCb_t$: state of charge of the local stationary battery.

External data provides the model parameters:

- $Consumption_t$: forecasted electrical consumption;
- $RES_generation_t$: forecasted renewable generation;
- ft : energy purchase price;
- c_t : energy selling or feed-in price;
- X_{MAX} : maximum capacity of the EV battery;
- $SoC_{b, max}$: maximum capacity of the local stationary battery;
- $P_{b, max}$: maximum power deliverable by the local stationary battery;
- $P_{ev, max}$: maximum charging power deliverable by the wallbox;
- Ep_t : Ev charger occupancy imported from Excel: 1 if the EV is connected, zero if it is not.

The optimisation problem is defined in four main phases:

1. Decision variables:

For each time interval, the optimisation determines the optimal energy flows uP , uN , power flows PEV , $Pbat$, and the state-of-charge values SoC , $SoCb$ that minimise the total energy cost while satisfying all system constraints.

2. Constraints:

Linear relationships among the decision variables represent all physical and operational constraints. The main energy balance equation ensures that, at every time interval, the power exchanged with the grid equals the difference between consumption, renewable generation, and the behaviour of the storage systems:

$$uP_t = Pev_t \cdot T + Consumption_t - RES_generation_t - Pbat_t \cdot T$$

Additional constraints define the upper limits of battery power, capacity, and state of charge:

$$0 \leq Pev \leq Pev_{max}$$

$$0 \leq Pbat \leq Pb_{max}$$

$$0 \leq SoC \leq X_{max}$$

$$0 \leq SoCb \leq SoCb_{max}$$

Two additional key equations follow, which govern the charging behaviour of both the EV and the stationary battery:

$$SoC_t = SoC_{t-1} + Pev_{t-1} \cdot Ep_{t-1} \cdot T$$

$$SoCb_t = SoCb_{t-1} - Pev_{t-1} \cdot Ep_{t-1} \cdot T$$

The auxiliary variables:

$$uPP = cp.\text{maximum}(uP, 0)$$

$$uN = cp.\text{maximum}(-uP, 0)$$

Here, *cp.maximum* is a function that returns the most significant value among the provided values.

- Objective function: The objective is to minimise the total energy cost over the entire set of time intervals:

$$\left[\sum_{t=1}^N (f_t \cdot uPP - c_t \cdot uN) + \lambda_1 \cdot \text{penalty1} + \lambda_2 \cdot \text{penalty2} + \lambda_3 \cdot \text{penalty3} \right]$$

Where λ_1 , λ_2 and λ_3 are penalty weights that ensure proper energy balancing and the stability of the state of charge.

- Penalty terms ensure that, while minimising costs:

In the next two equations, *xf* represents the EV disconnection instants,

$$\text{penalty1} = \sum_{xf} (0, XMAX - SoC_t)$$

The wallbox charges the EV as much as possible before departure,

$$\text{penalty2} = \sum_t (0, \frac{XMAX}{2} - SoC_t)$$

The wallbox charges the vehicle up to 50% of *XMAX* as soon as possible, in order to provide the user with a sufficiently charged car in case of need.

$$\text{penalty3} = \sum_t (SoCbmax_t - SoCb_t)$$

It has a very small λ_3 ; this ensures that excess energy is stored rather than sold, as storage is more advantageous.

5.5.3 Bidirectional optimization

In the bidirectional model, the EV is no longer considered solely as a load to be supplied; it becomes part of the system's set of storage resources.

The Wallbox is therefore managed as a reversible AC/DC converter, controlled by linear optimisation, which supports two operating modes:

1. Charging mode: The vehicle charges from the grid or from photovoltaic generation to reach the required state of charge by the scheduled departure time.
2. Discharging mode: When convenient or necessary (for instance, during consumption peaks, low production, or high prices), the algorithm may decide to partially discharge the EV battery, supplying energy to loads or helping reduce the power withdrawn from the grid.

This logic allows the electric vehicle to be integrated as a fully flexible energy resource, significantly increasing self-consumption capacity, operational flexibility, and the stability of the home energy profile.

Coordination with the stationary battery EV behaviour is optimised alongside the stationary battery. The model dynamically decides which storage system to use by evaluating:

- the residual state of charge of both batteries,
- the maximum deliverable power of each,
- the conversion efficiency,
- the energy prices,
- the expected photovoltaic production,
- the departure time of the electric vehicle.

In the presence of sudden load requirements or high prices, the model may favour discharging the EV rather than the stationary battery, or vice versa, depending on the optimal economic benefit.

Benefits of the bidirectional model: Introducing bidirectionality provides several advantages:

- increased self-consumed energy,
- reduction of peak grid withdrawals,
- improved system stability even during low renewable generation,
- intelligent integration of electric mobility as part of the energy system,
- further minimisation of total energy consumption.

In summary, the third algorithm represents an advanced extension of the applied linear optimisation logic: it integrates the electric vehicle not only as a consumption element but also as distributed, controllable storage capable of actively contributing to the system's energy balance. The actual change in the code concerns the constraint on the deliverable power limits of the wallbox, which is the following:

$$-P_{ev,max} \leq P_{ev} \leq P_{ev,max}$$

5.5.4 Management of Coordination Devices

After each iteration of the optimisation algorithm, the Coordination Devices are considered. The model allows the user to explicitly specify operational preferences, such as the connection and disconnection times of electric vehicles, as well as the desired state of charge at disconnection. The latter is modelled in the objective function via a high-weight penalty term to

drive the optimisation toward prioritising user preferences while remaining consistent with system constraints.

With respect to household coordination devices, such as the washing machine, the user can specify the earliest activation time t_{start} . Starting from this instant, the algorithm evaluates the activation of the device at every time step $t \in \{t_{\text{start}}, \dots, N\}$, identifying the most cost-effective starting time. Once the optimal activation time is determined, the consumption profile of the device is added to that of the No-Coordination Devices, thus becoming an integral part of the input vector Consumption_t . The optimisation algorithm is then executed again, considering the updated consumption profile.

Finally, the framework is designed to incorporate comfort-related user preferences, such as the desired indoor temperature of the dwelling, by incorporating them into the optimisation problem through appropriate constraints or penalty terms. In this way, the management of Coordination Devices is not driven exclusively by economic criteria but also reflects a trade-off between minimising energy costs and satisfying user preferences, making the system flexible and user-oriented.

5.6 Operation of an Optimised Residential Electrical Network

After describing the conventional operation of a residential energy system (5.3.1 Flow Management Logic), we now introduce how energy flow management changes when the proposed linear optimisation algorithm is applied.

The objective of the model is to predictively and dynamically coordinate flows between generation, storage systems, loads, and the grid, maximising self-consumption while minimising the total cost of purchased or sold electricity.

The optimisation simultaneously considers forecast data for demand (consumption), renewable generation, purchase and feed-in prices, and the SoC of the storage systems. Based on these parameters, the model determines, for each time interval, the optimal power values to be assigned to each device.

The overall system remains composed of the same physical components, but operational decisions are no longer reactive or locally determined; they are now globally coordinated and optimised.

5.6.1 Optimisation Algorithm Logic in Energy Flow Management:

1. PV Production

The optimisation model decides in real time how to allocate this energy among:

- direct supply to household loads;
- charging of storage batteries;
- injection into the grid.

Unlike conventional management, where surplus energy is automatically sent to the batteries or to the grid, the algorithm evaluates both the immediate and future economic convenience based on energy prices, consumption forecasts, and the batteries' SoC. In this way, it plans the most efficient operational strategy over time.

2. Self-consumption and household loads

Household loads remain the system's top energy priority.

The algorithm continuously compares the available PV power, the stored energy, and hourly prices, determining whether it is more advantageous to:

- supply the loads directly from renewable production;
- partially discharge the batteries;
- draw energy from the grid when prices are low, and the system predicts a more profitable use of storage in later periods.

In this way, the home-grid-battery energy balance is managed optimally, shifting from an instantaneous approach to a predictive and strategic one.

3. Management of Coordination Devices

The logic illustrated in 5.5.4 Management of Coordination Devices is followed.

4. Management of a stationary Battery and excess energy

The behaviour of the storage battery is no longer based on simple charge/discharge thresholds, but on an optimised strategy that takes into account:

- remaining capacity and maximum power limits;
- conversion efficiency;
- future energy prices and expected PV generation;
- load requirements during non-solar hours.

Through the constraints related to the batteries' state of charge and the objective function, the algorithm determines when to charge and when to discharge the batteries. In practice, the optimisation evaluates energy prices, available renewable generation and the technical limits of both storage systems to identify the most economical charging and discharging schedule over the time horizon.

For example, it may postpone charging when grid prices are high or anticipate discharging during a peak in demand.

5. EV charging management

The EV charging wallbox is integrated into the model as a flexible load.

The algorithm automatically decides when to start and stop charging while respecting the vehicle's arrival and departure times and the required state of charge.

The goal is to take advantage of low-price periods or periods of high renewable generation to charge the vehicle, thereby reducing costs and grid impact.

6. Optimised interaction with the grid

The interaction with the electrical grid becomes an active variable within the optimisation. The model computes the optimal profile of power import and export to minimise overall energy expenditure:

- When purchase prices are high, the algorithm reduces grid withdrawals by prioritising storage and self-consumption.
- When feed-in prices are favourable, and PV production is high, it maximises energy export to the grid.

The bidirectional meter continues to record energy exchanges, but a predictive and adaptive system now governs the dynamics.

7. Optimised priority logics

With the integration of the linear optimisation model, energy priorities are redefined as follows:

- a) Supply household loads with renewable energy, taking forecasts into account.
- b) Charge the batteries when production exceeds demand, and prices are low.
- c) Schedule battery discharge optimally to reduce costs during periods of high demand or high prices.
- d) Inject energy into the grid only when economically advantageous.
- e) Draw energy from the grid when necessary or convenient, based on price and consumption forecasts.

8. Overall view

In summary, the algorithm transforms the household system into an intelligent micro-energy unit capable of making optimal decisions at regular intervals, based on forecast data and technical constraints.

Each component is managed in an integrated, coordinated, and optimised manner, pursuing two fundamental objectives:

- reducing the household's overall energy costs;
- maximising autonomy and local self-consumption, while respecting system capacity and stability limits.

5.7 Experimental Results

The following figure presents the results obtained by the forecasting model described in *Section 4*.

Figure 14 - Forecast of Total Consumption, Renewable Generation and Energy Price During 36h

Figure 14 shows the corresponding forecast curves along with the trend of energy prices. The absolute value of the energy price is irrelevant to the explanation; what matters is the moment at which the price changes.

As explained in Section 5.2 Problem characterisation, the consumptions shown in Figure 14 refer to the No-Coordination Devices category.

To effectively test the algorithm, the following events were introduced:

- Two events involving devices categorised as Coordination Devices (one dishwasher cycle and one washing machine cycle) at time instants $t=1$ and $t=35$.
- Two EV charging events, with connections at $t=1$ and $t=49$ and disconnections at $t=9$ and $t=144$.

Below, we observe how the system handled the same input data across the three different algorithms presented.

Results: Uncoordinated strategy

Figure 15 – Consumption + Washing Machine + Dishwasher

Figure 15 shows the user’s consumption from the No-Coordination Devices, combined with the consumption of the two appliances (washing machine and dishwasher) categorised as Coordination Devices, at the previously indicated time instants.

Figure 16 - SoC of the PV Battery and Its Power Flow

Figure 16 shows the trend and management of the PV battery, which follows the logic illustrated in Section 5.3.1 Flow Management Logic: in fact, in the first part, the energy generated by the PV system is insufficient to meet the user’s demand, and therefore the batteries are discharged; whereas in the second part, there is a surplus of PV-generated energy that is used to recharge them.

Figure 17 - Temporal Evolution of the EV SoC & Charging Power

Figure 17 shows the EV's state of charge from the Wall Box perspective and the energy supplied to the EV by the latter. Therefore, SoC = 0 means that the EV is not connected to the Wall Box. As previously mentioned, there are two charging events.

We observe that it follows the logic illustrated in Section 0Flow Management Logic: that is, when the vehicle is connected, it is charged as much as possible.

In the uncoordinated case, the system behaves purely reactively rather than strategically. The stationary battery discharges whenever demand exceeds PV production and recharges only when surplus PV energy is available, without considering price dynamics. Similarly, the EV is charged at the maximum available power as soon as it is connected, independently of electricity prices or overall system conditions.

Overall, no cost-driven logic or coordinated balancing between loads, storage, and generation is applied.

5.7.1 Results: Unidirectional Optimisation

Figure 18 - Consumption + Washing Machine + Dishwasher

Figure 18 shows the user’s consumption from the No-Coordination Devices combined with the consumption of the two appliances (washing machine and dishwasher) categorised as Coordination Devices. The difference from what happens in the Uncoordinated Strategy is that the appliances are activated at different times, following the logic described in Section 5.5.4, Management of Coordination Devices.

Figure 19 - SoC of the PV Battery and Its Power Flow

Figure 19 shows the trend and management of the PV battery, which follows the logic described in Section 5.6.1 Optimisation Algorithm Logic in Energy Flow Management; in fact, even though energy demand is high during the night, the system does not use the PV batteries because it takes into account the lower price at that time and the expected demand during periods with higher costs.

Figure 20 - Temporal Evolution of the EV SoC & Charging Power

One can observe that during the first event, the power delivered is the same as in the *Uncoordinated Strategy* because, as explained in Section 5.5.2, the battery must be charged to 50% of its maximum capacity, i.e., 35 kWh. The differences appear in the second charging event, where the SoC curve no longer increases monotonically, even though it still reaches 100% charge. Instead, it exhibits variations because it follows the optimisation logic described above.

In the unidirectional optimisation case, the scheduling of household appliances is shifted toward more convenient time periods, as illustrated in Figure 18.

The stationary battery is managed more efficiently, with charging and discharging decisions driven not only by the instantaneous availability of PV energy but also by electricity prices and forecasted demand (Figures 19 and Figure 20).

The EV charging process is also controlled and distributed over time, in contrast to the immediate full-power charging observed in the uncoordinated strategy.

As a result, the system reduces energy withdrawals during high-price periods, achieving a more cost-effective operating profile.

5.7.2 Results: Bidirectional Optimisation

Figure 21 - Consumption + Washing Machine + Dishwasher

Figure 21 shows the user’s consumption from the No-Coordination Devices combined with the consumption of the two appliances (washing machine and dishwasher) categorised as Coordination Devices. The difference from what happens in the Uncoordinated Strategy is that the appliances are activated at different times, following the logic described in Section 5.5.4, Management of Coordination Devices.

Figure 22 - SoC of the PV Battery and Its Power Flow

Figure 22 shows the trend and management of the PV battery, which follows the logic described in Section 5.6.1 Optimisation Algorithm Logic in Energy Flow Management; in fact, even though energy demand is high during the night, the system does not use the PV batteries, on the contrary, it recharges them, because it takes into account the lower price at that time and the expected demand during periods with higher costs.

Figure 23 - Temporal Evolution of the EV SoC & Charging Power

Figure 23 has the same meaning as Figure 20. In addition to managing the charging process by varying the delivered power, the EV also absorbs power when necessary, making it an active load and reaching SoC = 100% at the disconnection instant.

In the bidirectional optimisation scenario, the EV becomes an active energy resource that helps cover demand peaks, as shown in Figure 23.

The stationary battery is also operated more strategically, with charging and discharging patterns optimised to maximise economic benefits and system efficiency.

This coordinated use of both storage systems results in greater cost reductions and increased local energy autonomy than in previous cases.

Overall, the system exhibits markedly different behaviour from the unidirectional strategy, thanks to the EV's ability to both absorb and supply energy when advantageous.

5.7.3 Comparison of the results of the three algorithms

Figure 24 - Comparison of absolute and relative energy costs for three strategies.

Figure 24 shows the cost differences among the three methods. The absolute value is of limited interest given the synthetic data employed. However, the percentage difference between the three methods shows a cost reduction within the 36 hours considered for both optimisation strategies.

Although the values shown are based on synthetic data, the observed cost reduction (approximately 6–8% over 36 hours) would translate into an estimated monthly saving of

around 8–12% for a typical household, depending on consumption patterns, seasonal variability, and local energy prices.

Figure 25 - Comparison of absolute and relative energy consumption for 3 strategies

Figure 25 shows the differences in grid energy consumption among the three methods. The absolute value is of limited interest given the synthetic data employed. However, the percentage difference between the three methods shows a reduction within the 36 hours considered for both optimisation strategies.

6. Control of Energy Flux

The system is presented in 5. The optimisation model highlights that, to optimise the user's electricity consumption, both a self-generation unit and an energy storage system are essential. The core of the microgrid is the inverter, which serves as the central energy controller, coordinating PV generation, storage, household loads, and possible grid exchanges, enabling the practical implementation of the optimal strategies computed by the algorithm. A control architecture is currently being developed with POLITO, enabling the inverter to be effectively driven by the algorithm outputs to test its capabilities.

The algorithm's outputs will be sent to an Edge Gateway, which will translate them into CAN protocols to control the inverter's energy distribution.

Figure 26 - Deployment view

7. Integrations with Other Modules

The AI-based assistant module developed in Task 2.3 operates as an intelligent layer within the broader EU-DREAM architecture, closely integrated with the digital twin ecosystem and user-facing components of the project. Its core role is to transform the data and simulation capabilities of the Digital Twin environment into actionable, human-centred energy services. This integration is achieved through a continuous exchange of data and control signals between the AI module and these other major subsystems:

1. **The Digital Twin (DT)** – as described in D2.1 - represents the physical and behavioural dynamics of the Living Labs. These models replicate the operation of household appliances, distributed energy resources (such as PV and wind systems), and the thermal behaviour of buildings. The DTs provide the *virtual ground truth* on which the AI assistant learns, forecasts, and validates its optimisation outcomes.
2. **The Digital Twin Infrastructure and Orchestrator** – The orchestrator reported in D2.2 ensures that data flow between modules follows a consistent, traceable workflow. It provides APIs for data access, controls simulation execution, and manages all inbound and outbound messages involving the AI module. Through this layer, the assistant receives the operational and environmental data required for forecasting and optimisation, and returns the resulting schedules, set points, or recommendations for further processing and validation.
3. **The NLP-based Intermediator (T2.4)** provides a natural-language interface that enables end users to interact with the AI assistant via text commands. When a user submits a request (e.g., “optimise my consumption for tomorrow”), the NLP module interprets it, converts it into structured data, and triggers the corresponding AI process via the orchestrator. Once the AI module generates a result, the NLP component reformulates it into a readable, context-aware message, adapting the language, terminology, and technical level to the specific user profile. This system is better described in D2.4.

This interconnected architecture enables a fully functional human-in-the-loop system. Forecasts generated by the AI module can be validated in the DT environment before being applied in real scenarios; decisions can be simulated and their outcomes visualised; and user feedback collected through the NLP interface can be used to refine future predictions and recommendations.

All these interactions occur through the Digital Twin Orchestrator, which guarantees synchronisation, reproducibility, and data integrity across the distributed system.

The following sections illustrate three concrete examples of the AI module's utilisation in combination with other models.

7.1 Example 1 – Forecasting Loop (Prediction and Validation)

The forecasting routines within the assistant use both real and simulated data supplied by the DT Infrastructure.

Weather information (e.g., irradiance, temperature, wind speed) is retrieved from open data sources such as Open-Meteo. At the same time, contextual variables (consumption, PV output) come from the DT models of the Living Labs.

The forecasting models process these inputs developed under T2.3, such as LightGBM-based predictors for load, PV, and wind generation, to produce day-ahead and intra-day predictions. For example, *Figure 27* illustrates how the predicted PV generation profile aligns with the simulated household demand curve, showing potential for self-consumption and reduced grid dependency.

Figure 27 - Potential for Load Shift Optimization

7.2 Example 2 – Optimisation Loop (Decision Support in Action)

In the EU-DREAM workflow, the optimisation process relies on receiving new operational information regarding the status of household devices. These inputs may also be provided directly by the user during everyday activities. Typical examples include:

- informing the system that an EV has been connected and will be disconnected at a specific time;
- indicating that a washing machine or dishwasher has been loaded and is ready to operate;
- specifying that a flexible appliance can be run within a specific time window.

These user actions are captured through the NLP interface, which interprets them as structured events and forwards them to the Digital Twin Orchestrator. The orchestrator activates the corresponding optimisation pipeline within the AI module, which executes the algorithm at a defined temporal cadence.

Once triggered, the optimisation engine uses the most recent forecasts (demand, PV production, wind generation) together with the available operational constraints (EV connection time, appliance readiness, battery SoC, energy prices) to compute the most cost-efficient and self-consumption-oriented schedule for controllable devices.

Figure 28 - 3 case studies: consumption

	NO Optimization	Monodirectional	Bidirectional
Battery Cycles	0	0	4

Figure 29 - 3 case studies: SoC storage + Battery cycles

Figure 30 - 3 case studies: SoC of EV

From the previous figures, the three different scenarios can be observed:

- Figure 28 shows the energy consumption of both the No-Coordination Devices and the Coordination Devices.
- Cycles illustrate the state of charge of the storage system and the corresponding battery cycles, which must be taken into account when evaluating the optimisation's validity.
- Figure 30 shows the EV's state of charge during charging.

This allows us to observe how the different optimisation logics exploit the available devices.

7.3 Example 3 – User Interaction and Feedback Loop

The results of forecasting and optimisation are communicated to the user through the NLP-based intermediary.

Here, technical outputs are translated into human-readable recommendations, tailored to the user's language, literacy level, and preferences (e.g., *"Charging your EV between 13:00 and 16:00 will maximise solar self-use and reduce grid costs by 12%"*). This ensures transparency, accessibility, and trust in the AI system.

User Interaction and Feedback Flow

Figure 31 - Interaction Workflow Among DT, Orchestrator, AI Forecast, AI Optimisation, and NLP Interface

Conversely, user feedback—such as approval, rejection, or fine-tuning of proposed actions—is captured by the NLP interface and used to update preferences or constraints in subsequent optimisation cycles.

This interaction fosters a dynamic learning loop where the AI continuously adapts to user behaviour, ensuring relevance and personalisation across Living Labs. The interaction is visually explained in *Figure 31*

8. Conclusions

The work presented in this deliverable provides a comprehensive foundation for the AI-based assistant tool developed under Task 2.3. It demonstrates how forecasting, optimisation, and user-centred interaction can be integrated into a unified digital energy service within the EU-DREAM ecosystem.

By developing modular forecasting models for electrical demand, solar PV, and wind generation, the assistant establishes a reliable predictive layer that supports day-ahead and intra-day decision-making. The results obtained with LightGBM confirm that robust and computationally efficient forecasting is achievable even in data-scarce environments, ensuring scalability across all Living Labs.

Building on these predictions, the linear optimisation engine implements a flexible, interpretable decision-support mechanism that coordinates household devices, storage systems, and EV charging over a 36-hour horizon. By adopting an entirely linear formulation with soft constraints, the model avoids the need for commercial MIP solvers while still enabling the orchestration of complex behaviours such as coordinated appliance scheduling, dynamic battery management, and both unidirectional and bidirectional EV charging. The experimental scenarios demonstrate clear improvements in cost savings, self-consumption, and load shifting, showing how different optimisation logics exploit domestic resources in distinct ways.

All forecasting and optimisation routines operate within an orchestrated workflow, in which the NLP interface ensures that user actions (e.g., EV connection, appliance readiness) are translated into structured events that automatically trigger optimisation cycles. This creates a fully operational human-in-the-loop system, where technical outputs are validated and presented back to the end users in an accessible and personalised manner.

The collaboration with WP6 further ensures that the assistant tool is grounded in real user needs, literacy levels, and behavioural patterns. The survey insights and qualitative feedback collected from Living Labs guide the design of objectives, communication styles, and interaction mechanisms, making the assistant not only a technical optimisation layer but also a tool for enhancing energy literacy, awareness, and engagement.

The tool provides a solid foundation for future developments, including real-data calibration, validation in Living Labs, and adaptation to diverse European households, ultimately supporting consumers and communities in becoming active, informed, and empowered participants in the energy transition.

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